

ON THE BEHAVIOR OF SOLUTIONS OF THE CROSS DIFFUSION SYSTEM

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In this paper, we studied the qualitative properties of solutions of a nonlinear cross-diffusion system coupled via nonlinear boundary conditions

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\nu^{m_1-1} \left| \frac{\partial u^k}{\partial x} \right|^{p-2} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right), & x \in R_+, t > 0, \\ \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(u^{m_2-1} \left| \frac{\partial \nu^k}{\partial x} \right|^{p-2} \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \right), & x \in R_+, t > 0, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{cases} -\nu^{m_1-1} \left| \frac{\partial u^k}{\partial x} \right|^{p-2} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}(0, t) = u^{q_1}(0, t), & t > 0, \\ -u^{m_2-1} \left| \frac{\partial \nu^k}{\partial x} \right|^{p-2} \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x}(0, t) = \nu^{q_2}(0, t), & t > 0, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$u(x, 0) = u_0(x), \quad \nu(x, 0) = \nu_0(x), \quad x \in R_+, \quad (3)$$

where $k, p, m_1, m_2 > 0, q_1, q_2 > 0, u_0, \nu_0$ are nonnegative continuous functions with compact supports in R_+ .

Cross-diffusion patterns are found in various spheres of natural sciences. For example, in physical systems (plasma physics) [1, 3], in chemical systems (dynamics of electrolytic solutions), in biological systems (cross-diffusion transportation, dynamics of population systems), in ecology (dynamics of the forest age structure), in seismology – the Burridge-Knopoff model describing the interaction of tectonic plates. Mathematical models with cross diffusion are widely used in the study of biological population and tectonic plate movement [3]. The study of the conditions of global solvability and insolubility of problem (1) - (3) for various values of numerical parameters has been the subject of a large number of papers [2-6] (for details see the reference [3, 6]).

This paper is devoted to the study of the asymptotics of a self-similar solution of problem (1) - (3). Various self-similar solutions of problem (1) - (3) are constructed for the case of slow diffusion ($m_1, m_2 > 1$), which are the asymptotics of the solutions of the problem in question. For a numerical study, the methods are proposed for selecting the appropriate initial approximation for the iterative

process, which preserve the qualitative properties of problem (1) - (3). An iterative process was designed and numerical calculations, showing rapid convergence to the exact solution, were performed.

REFERENCES

1. Wu, Z.Q., Zhao, J.N., Yin, J.X. and Li, H.L., Nonlinear Diffusion Equations, Singapore: World Scientific, 2001.
2. Zheng S N, Song X F, Jiang Z X. Critical Fujita exponents for degenerate parabolic equations coupled via nonlinear boundary flux. J Math Analysis Appl, 2004, 298: 308–324.
3. M.A. Tsyganov, V.N. Biktashev, J. Brindley, A.V. Holden, G.R. Ivanitsky, Waves in cross-diffusion systems – a special class of nonlinear waves, UFN, 2007, vol. 177, issue 3, 275-300.
4. Rakhmonov Z. Estimates for the solutions of a nonlinear system of the heat equation with variable density and with a nonlocal boundary condition. Bulletin of the NUU, No. 1 (2), 2016, 145-154.
5. Aripov M.M., Matyakubov A.S. To the qualitative properties of solution of system equations not in divergence form of polytrophic filtration in variable density. Nanosystems: Physics, Chemistry, Mathematics, 2017, 8(3), 317-322.
6. Anita Gerstenmayer, AnsgarJüngel. Analysis of a degenerate parabolic cross-diffusion system for ion transport. Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications, Volume 461, Issue 1, 1 May 2018, Pages 523-543.